

COESO

connecting research and society

COLLABORATIVE ENGAGEMENT ON SOCIETAL ISSUES

WP2 - Pilot implementation and Open Call Solution journalism outputs

date 28.06.2022

This deliverable is licenced under
a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence.

COESO has received funding from the EU Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme (2014-2020)
SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation, under Grant Agreement No.101006325

The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the COESO consortium and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Deliverable 2.7

Solution journalism outputs

Grant Agreement number	: 101006325
Project acronym	: COESO
Project title	: Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues
Funding Scheme	: H2020-EU.5. - SCIENCE WITH AND FOR SOCIETY
Topic	: SwafS-27-2020 - Hands-on citizen science and frugal innovation
Project's coordinator Organization	: EHESS-OpenEdition
E-mail address	: pierre.mounier@openedition.org , alessia.smaniotto@openedition.org
Website	: https://coeso.hypotheses.org
WP and tasks contributing	: WP2 - Pilot implementation and Open Call
WP leader	: CRIA
Task leader	: Cafébabel
Dissemination level	: PU
Due date	: 30.06.2022
Delivery date	: 28.06.2022
Author	: Mathilde Docardie (CafeBabel)
Contributor	: Fabrice Rizzoli (Crim'HALT)
Reviewers	: Francesca Festa (CafeBabel), Baptistin Hin (EHESS-OpenEdition), Elisa Lopes da Silva (CRIA)
English proofreading	: Pierre Mounier (EHESS-Open Edition)

Contents

Contextualisation	4
Description of the project	4
Background of the project	4
Conduct of the field work	4
Communication and dissemination of the outcomes	6
Content produced	6
Dissemination of the content	9
Online dissemination	9
Academic dissemination	9

I. Contextualisation

Description of the project

Background of the project

This deliverable documents the work developed in the context of the collaborative project “Social impacts of redistributing property confiscated from the mafia”, the Pilot 3 of the European project on citizen science COESO. This collaborative research was carried out between Cafébabel, an online magazine, and Crim’HALT, an association to develop effective “Solutions Journalism” strategies. The document provides a description of the project, of the conduction of fieldwork and attests the dissemination of research outcomes in the form of magazine’s articles and academic lectures. Targeted groups/involved citizens: residents of areas impacted by organized crime, policymakers, apprentice journalists, scientific journalists.

The Italian law against organised crime is the strongest and the most effective in the UE. Its main objective consists in confiscation (art. 416 bis Italian penal code in 1982) and social reuse of assets from organised crime (law 109/1996). By such a policy, what is confiscated from crime is given back visibly to society, by allowing confiscated property to be used for public interest or social purposes, hence could be directly assigned, free of charge, to NGOs. Through this Pilot, Babel International (Cafebabel), in collaboration with the independent research center CrimeHALT 39, has tried to define the role of civil society in promoting good governance and the economic aspect of such a policy. The Pilot supports the promotion, development and implementation of this methodology in other cultural spheres around Europe, thanks to the opportunities that “solution journalism” can bring. Solution Journalism is critical reporting that investigates and explains credible responses to social issues. Two field works were conducted in Italy. The first field studied was Casal di Principe in Campania, where a large number of social enterprises operating in property confiscated from organised crime are concentrated in the same area. In 2019, the antimafia mayor was re-elected for a second mandate. The second field is the city of Genoa, which has undertaken to rehabilitate the old city center.

Conduct of the field work

The project was conducted in two steps :

1) The first field work was conducted in **Casal di Principe** in Campania between the 30th of June and the 7th of July 2021 by the researcher and the journalist. Casal di Principe was chosen as a sample because of its past as a former stronghold of the Camorra organisation. It is now known as an anti-mafia stronghold, as explained by its mayor Renato Natale who was interviewed in the frame of the field work, and it is seen as an example in Italy. This city has been also chosen for its good implementation of the laws on social reuse of confiscated assets. The aim was to conduct 8 interviews of residents of this area, as well as policy makers in order to assess the impact of social reuse of assets from organised crime in this region: citizens, academics, political and associative leaders, users/employees of projects related to confiscated assets...

At the entrance to the town, a sign reminds visitors that Casal di Principe is committed to fighting crime, with the slogan "United in legality, we grow" and a tribute to the priest Giuseppe Diana, murdered by the mafia in 1994 (photo: M.D./Coeso)

2) The second field work was conducted in **Genoa** in Liguria between the 9th and the 15th of November 2021 by the researcher and the journalist. To balance the field work conducted in Casal di Principe, Genoa was chosen because it is an example of the difficulty of fully implementing laws on the reuse of confiscated assets in the field in Italy. That is notably the work of the association Libera to advocate for a more extensive application of the law. The journalist and the researcher collaborated with Libera to conduct this field work and interviewed activists in the frame of this research. The aim was to conduct 8 interviews of residents of this area, as well as policy makers in order to assess the impact of and social reuse of assets from organised crime in this region: citizens, academics, political and associative leaders, users/employees of projects related to confiscated assets..

Meeting with the regional referent of Libera, Stefano Busi, who introduced the researcher and the journalist to the situation of Liguria, followed by a tour in the city with social workers who take care of people rehoused in apartments confiscated by justice from slum landlords.

II. Communication and dissemination of the outcomes

Content produced

After assessing and gathering data and information, the journalist worked on and produced a series of articles (3) "*New Landlords, when the Italian civil society moves in with the mafia*". to publicise the data analysed. The journey was described step-by-step in an online diary, available [here](#).

The [first article](#) was published on **28th April 2022** and was dedicated to unfold the results of the field work from a journalistic perspective, including 8 interviews of citizens, academics, political and associative leaders, users/employees of projects related to confiscated assets... conducted in Casal di Principe

The image shows two screenshots of the CAFEBABEL website. The top screenshot displays a news article snippet with the headline: « Réutiliser les biens, ce n'est pas important, c'est fondamental ! » (1/3). Below the headline, it says "Published on April 28, 2022" and "Story by Mathilde Dorcadie". The bottom screenshot shows the same article page with a description: "Changement de propriétaire : quand la société civile italienne s'installe chez les mafieux" est la série de Cafébabel sur des citoyens qui réinvestissent les biens du crime organisé confisqués par la justice. Comment et pourquoi créer des projets pour le bien commun dans des lieux qui ont, par le passé, servis les intérêts des mafieux? Dans ce premier volet de notre enquête, nous partons en reportage dans l'arrière pays napolitain.

The [second article](#) was published on **12th May 2022** and was dedicated to unfold the results of the field work conducted in Genoa between the 9th and the 15th of November by the researcher and the journalist from a journalistic perspective, including 8 interviews of citizens, academics, political and associative leaders, users/employees of projects related to confiscated assets... and continue the experimentation conducted before in Casa di Principale.

The image shows two screenshots of the CAFEBABEL website. The top screenshot displays the article header with the title: « Ceci n'est pas une devanture, c'est un bien confisqué, une ressource de la communauté » (2/3). It includes the author's name, Mathilde Dorcadie, and the publication date, May 13, 2022. The bottom screenshot shows the same article header but with a quote below it: "Changement de propriétaire : quand la société civile italienne s'installe chez les mafieux" est la série de Cafébabel sur des citoyens qui réinvestissent les biens du crime organisé confisqués par la justice. Comment et pourquoi créer des projets pour le bien commun dans des lieux qui ont, par le passé, servis les intérêts des mafieux? Pour le second volet de notre enquête, nous explorons la ville de Gênes.

FR Participate Translate CAFEBABEL

« Ceci n'est pas une devanture, c'est un bien confisqué, une ressource de la communauté » (2/3)

Published on May 13, 2022

Story by Mathilde Dorcadie

#changement de propriétaire #Corruption

FR Participate Translate CAFEBABEL

Mathilde Dorcadie

#changement de propriétaire #Corruption

fr es it de pl

"Changement de propriétaire : quand la société civile italienne s'installe chez les mafieux" est la série de Cafébabel sur des citoyens qui réinvestissent les biens du crime organisé confisqués par la justice. Comment et pourquoi créer des projets pour le bien commun dans des lieux qui ont, par le passé, servis les intérêts des mafieux? Pour le second volet de notre enquête, nous explorons la ville de Gênes.

The [third article](#) was published on **26th May 2022**. It analyses the limits of the reuse of the assets of organised crime confiscated by the justice system. It gives the voice to associations and volunteers who advocate for a more extensive application of the law in Italy.

« Quand on gère un bien confisqué, il faut faire ses preuves. C'est une question de crédibilité face à ce qu'on combat » (3/3)

Published on May 26, 2022

Story by

Mathilde Dorcadie

FR

CAFEBABEL

fr en es it de pl

Dernier épisode de notre série "Changement de propriétaire : quand la société civile italienne s'installe chez les mafieux", l'enquête de Cafébabel sur des citoyens qui réinvestissent les biens du crime organisé confisqués par la justice. On retrouve dans toute l'Italie des centaines de réinvestissements d'anciens biens de la mafia par des associations. Mais les bénévoles et associations regrettent un manque d'accompagnement des pouvoirs publics.

Il est tout juste **7 heures** du matin et c'est l'effervescence dans l'atelier de production. Une à une, les petites boules blanches plongent dans la saumure, à peine modelées par la machine. La deuxième livraison de mozzarellas de la matinée est bientôt prête à partir pour fournir restaurants et épiceries de Rome et au-delà. **Massimo Rocco** observe les gestes experts de ses trois employés, l'air confiant de celui qui sait que tout se déroule

Dissemination of the content

The content was disseminated online as well as offline.

Online dissemination

It was published on the website cafébabel.com but also promoted throughout our social media platforms on Facebook, [Twitter](#), [Instagram](#) and [LinkedIn](#).

The journalist and the researcher also used their social media to promote their work, in particular through [twitter](#). The researcher also disseminated the project via the [website](#) of CrimHalt, and published the article on Monday the 20th of June 2022. It was also disseminated on CrimHalt social media : [Facebook](#), [Twitter](#), [Youtube](#) and [Instagram](#). Two newsletters will also be sent to the CrimHalt segment (approx. 4000 subscribers) to promote this series of articles on the 21st of June 2022.

All the articles were written and published in the mother tongue of the journalist and the researcher : French. The translation to English, Italian and German is in process and will be published by the 30th of June 2022 on the website and social media platforms.

Academic dissemination

Four lectures were organised by the researcher both online and offline to disseminate, promote and present the outcome of the project :

1/ Online Lectures

- One took place [online](#) on the 11th January 2022, in partnership with “Solidarités Nouvelles pour le Logement”, in the frame of the meeting : “*Rencontres de l'habitat solidaire*”:

- [A workshop](#) was also organised online with alumni from Sciences Po Paris, in order to provide them insights on the topic of reuse of confiscated assets in Italy. This event took place on the 15th, March 2022

2/ Offline Lectures

- A [lecture](#) was also organised in Science Po Paris by “La strada” (Franco-Italian association from Sciences Po Paris) on the theme of the Italian mafia on the 15th February 2022 and presented the reuse of confiscated assets publicly and the first outcomes of the COESO project.

- The researcher will also give a training with the Agence de gestion et de recouvrement des avoirs saisis et confisqués (AGRASC) on wednesday 29th June 2022.

Note : All these events took place in France, some others are foreseen in Italy when the articles will be translated.

Network dissemination

The researcher and the journalist, as well as Cafébabel team also disseminated information about the project through their network by sharing articles and explanations of the project via LinkedIn or Whatsapp groups.